

Unity and Diversity in Indian society

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Abstract: India is a plural society. It is rightly characterized by its unity and diversity. we will illustrate the forms of diversity in Indian society. For detailed treatment we will focus on the four forms of diversity, race, language, religion and caste., we will bring out the bonds of unity in India. These are geopolitical, the culture of pilgrimage, tradition of accommodation, and tradition of interdependence. A grand synthesis of cultures, religions and languages of the people belonging to different castes and communities has upheld its unity and cohesiveness. In spite of several foreign invasions, Mughal rule and the British rule, national unity and integrity have been maintained. India fought against the British Rule as one unified entity. Foreign invasions, immigration from other parts of the world, and the existence of diverse languages, cultures and religions have made India's culture tolerant, on the one hand, and a unique continuing and living culture, with its specificity and historicity, on the other. Hinduism, Jainism, Buddhism, Islam, Sikhism and Christianity are the major religions. There is diversity not only in regard to racial compositions, religious and linguistic distinction but also in patterns of living, life styles, land tenure systems, occupational pursuits, inheritance and succession law, and practices and rites related to birth, marriage death etc. Post-Independent India is a nation united against several odds and obstacles. The Five Year Plans and several other developmental schemes are geared to the upliftment of the poor and weaker sections of society.

Unity means integration. It is a social psychological condition. It stands for the bonds, which hold the members of a society together. Unity in diversity essentially means "unity without uniformity" and "diversity without fragmentation". It is based on the notion that diversity enriches human interaction. When we say that India is a nation of great cultural diversity, we mean that there are many different types of social groups and communities living here. These are communities defined by cultural markers such as language, religion, sect, race or caste.

Objectives

They follow different religions of their choice because India is a secular country.

Being related to different cultures, languages and religions, people here respect each other and live with a feeling of love and brotherhood.

India, 5000 years old civilization is a land of diversities, be it religion, caste, race, culture or language, there are many variations in the country.

There are about 29 states and each state has its own culture, tradition and language.

Every year more than 30 grand festivals of various communities are celebrated in the country.

Despite such a difference, the people of India demonstrate a genuine sense of unity among themselves which reflects the concept of unity in diversity.

Unity in India's diversity culture is considered unique in the world which surprises the global community.

This is due to the age-old tradition of India which has taught people the importance of morality, values, respect and tolerance.

Although people belonging to diverse cultures and communities, they share the bond of humanity, love, respect and are bound by the same strand of nationalism.

People in all parts of this country join with the faith of brotherhood.

Unity in diversity is a great feature of our nation because people of different religions have been in a bond of humanity for many years.

describe the forms and bases of diversity in India

examine the bonds and mechanisms of unity in India

provide an explanation to our option for a composite culture model rather than a uniformity model of unity.

Concepts Of Unity And Diversity

Meaning of Diversity Ordinarily diversity means differences. For our purposes, however, it means something more than mere differences. It means collective differences, that is, differences which mark off one group of people from another. These differences may be of any sort: biological, religious, linguistic etc. On the basis of biological differences, for example, we have

racial diversity. On the basis of religious differences, similarly, we have religious diversity. The point to note is that diversity refers to collective differences. The term diversity is opposite of uniformity. Uniformity means similarity of some sort that characterizes a people. 'Uni' refers to one; 'form' refers to the common ways. So when there is something common to all the people, we say they show uniformity. When students of a school, members of the police or the army wear the same type of dress, we say they are in 'uniform'. Like diversity, thus, uniformity is also a collective concept. When a group of people share a similar characteristic, be it language or religion or anything else, it shows uniformity in that respect. But when we have groups of people hailing from different races, religions and cultures, they represent diversity.

Factors influences to unity in diversity

The sources of diversity in India may be traced through a variety of ways, the most obvious being the ethnic origins, religious, castes, tribes, languages, social customs, cultural and subcultural beliefs, political philosophies and ideologies, geographical variations etc.

Racial Diversity: Dr.B.S.Guha: The classifications, has presented his own list of races that are believed to have composed the Indian population. 1. The Negrito: The presence of a Negrito substratum in Indian population is a controversial issue among the anthropologists 2. The Proto-Australoid or the Pre-Dravidian: Indian tribal population by and large is dominated by this racial element. 3. The Mongoloid: This race came into India from North-Western China via Tibet. People having this racial ancestry are mainly found in North-Eastern India. This race is found to consist two fundamental types namely (a) The Palaeo-Mongoloid: there are two sub-types of the palaeo mongoloid branch of mongoloid race : one is the long headed type and the other is the broadheaded type. (b) The Tibeto-Mongoloid: The people of Sikkim and Bhutan are said to the Tibeto Mongoloid branch of mongoloid race. 4. The Mediterranean: This race is one of the dominant races in India. This race is divided into Three types. They are: (a) The Palaeo Mediterranean: This racial type is represented by the Tamil and Telugu Brahmins of the South. 7 (b) The Mediterranean: people of this racial type are

believed to be the builders of the Indus Valley Civilization. (c) Oriental: This race groups are very much similar to the Mediterranean racial type. 5. Western Brachycephals: This race entered India from the West. The Alpinoid, the Dinaric and the Armenoid are three main types of this race (a) Alpinoid: the people of Saurashtra, Gujarat and also Bengal are said to have this strain in their blood. (b) Dinaric: This strain is claimed to be found among the peoples of Odisha, Bengal and Coorg. (c) Armenoid: the Parsees of Bombay are believed to be the true representatives of this racial type. 6. Nordic race: people belonging to this race came to India from the North and spread all over Northern India.

2: Religious diversity: India is a land of multiple religions. Apart from the tribal societies, many of whom still live in the pre-religious state of animism and magic, the Indian population consists of the Hindus (82.41%), Muslims (11.6%), Christians (2.32%), Sikhs (1.99%), Buddhists (0.77%) and Jains (0.41%). The Hindus themselves are divided into several sects such as Vaishnavas, Shaivates, Shaktas, Smartas etc. Similarly, the Muslims are divided into sects such as Shias, Sunnis, Ahmadiyas etc. **Linguistic diversity:** Languages spoken in India belong to several language families, the m

3. Linguistic Diversity: India is called a 'veritable tower of Babel' and according to A. R. Desai, "India presents a spectacle of Museum of tongues." The 1971 census reports the presence of 1652 languages in India. Most of the languages are spoken in the North India. This multiplicity of languages creates new social cleavages in the already divided population of India by caste and creed and renders the task of inter-communication in the country difficult, if not impossible. 10 Indian languages can, however, be grouped into four different speech families such as:(1) the Indo-Aryan, (2) the Dravidian, (3) the Austric and (4) the Sino-Tibetan. Hindi, Urdhu, Punjabi, Assamese, Bengali, Odia, Gujarathi, Marathi and Kashmiri belong to the Indo-Aryan speech family. The Dravidian linguistic group includes four southern languages namely, Tamil, Telugu, Kannada and Malayalam. The tribes of central India speak Austric languages and the tribes of the North Eastern India speak the Sino-Tibetan

languages Though the Constitution of India has recognized 22 major languages, as many as 1652 languages spoken in our country. Broadly these languages belong to three families of languages such as Indo-Aryan, Dravidian and European. Hindi, Bengali, Marathi, Gujarati, Odia, Punjabi, Bihari, Rajasthani, Assamese, Sanskrit, Sindhi and Kashmiri are included in the Indo-Aryan family. The Dravidian language includes Tamil, Telugu, Malayalam and Kannada. English, Portuguese and French are included in the European language family. Portuguese and French are mostly spoken by people in Goa and Pondicherry respectively. Hindi has been accepted as the official language in India

Various Factors leadings to Unity in India

Geographical unity: India, though very large in size, possesses geographical unity with natural boundaries. It is surrounded on one side by the great Himalayas and on the other sides by the high seas. These natural boundaries give the land geographical unity. The term 'Bharat Varsha' i.e, India has always referred to this vast expanse of, the land expanding from the Himalayas in the North to the Cape Comorin in the south and from the Brahmaputra in the East to the Indus in the West. Religious thinkers, political philosophers, poets, statesmen and kings have always conceived Bharat Varsha in this sense. Even today, Mother India means this vast expanse of land.

India may not be a mixed by itself but from times ancient India has been considered as one country. The only name Bharatvarsha has granted to this country emphasis this unity.

The rivers of India are also responsible for giving a sense of unity to the country. Some of the rivers are of divine origin and are considered sacred by all Indians. For example, Ganga is worshipped in all the four corners. Pilgrims from all over the country continue to visit the shrines standing on their banks. Other rivers, such as the Yamuna and Saraswati rivers, are also considered sacred by the people throughout the country. In short, we can say that despite the geographical diversity the country has enjoyed a common sense of unity.

Linguistic unity: Although India maintains a variety of language, According to Dr Ray Chaudhri, "Prakrit was the one only

language enough to bring the information of a royal minister to the bars of his enduring subject during this huge kingdom." After Prakrit, Sanskrit became the common language

of the masses. Another local language which subsequently realised influence began out of Sanskrit. Some of the leading Indian languages which owe their rise to Sanskrit include Hindi, Gujarati, Telugu and Tamil. Sanskrit followed as the lingua franca throughout ancient times.

Throughout the Medieval times also though the Sanskrit language was not spread royal support by the Muslim rulers, the rulers in the South continued to favour it and it continued to increase. With the coming of the British, English shifted lingua franca. After independence, this role has been carried over by Hindi. The text of the various languages used in India also maintains a certain amount of regularity. Almost all the texts are based on the Brahmin script. The literature originated in different Indian languages also maintains a component of unity.

Fairs and festivals: They also act as integrating factors as people from all parts of the country celebrate them as per their own local customs. Eg. Diwali is celebrated throughout by Hindus in the country; similarly Id and Christmas are celebrated by Muslims and Christians, respectively. Celebration of inter-religious festivals is also seen in India.

Religious and social Unity

In the religious sphere and in spite of diversity, the type of unity has grown among the various religious denominations in that country. People in all four corners of the globe followed these principles. People also worship the same Hindu deities throughout the land, although they are assigned different names in different names in different regions. The Hindu religious activities of Ramayana and Mahabharata were also popular throughout the country and the Indians in the north and south, as well as in the east and west, placed great importance on these activities.

Hindu festivals like Holi, Diwali are also celebrated in all religions of the country. People of all faiths are involved in this celebration. We, therefore, find that despite the diversity of religions there is a great diversity of cultures that is largely influenced by the diversity of religions.

Political unity

In the political arena In ancient times, Chandra Gupta Maurya, Ashoka and Samundra Gupta brought out all the Indian Empires. During ancient times, Ala-ud-Din-Khilji and Aurangzeb made efforts and succeeded in establishing their rule throughout the country. These Muslim rulers were provided with a common system of governance, common laws and customs, common gatherings etc, and thus introduced a form of political unity throughout the country. We therefore find that although there are different religions, cultures, languages, geographical diversity, etc. India had enjoyed some kind of unity.

Conclusion

Unity in diversity instructs us that although we are from diverse caste, creed or race, these variations cannot keep us apart and we are eternally united for the improvement of our nation. This is the most uncommon event which is exposed in our country. It not only performs the nation united and strengthened but it also holds us alive in the old eras, the belief of co-existence with love, peace, and respect. The distinction in culture, traditions, festivals, music and dance makes the country energetic and makes an unbelievable country in the world.

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